

Original Research

A Theoretical Framework for Autonomous Vehicles: A Sustainability Perspective

Esther Chota¹

School of Economics and Management, Chang'an University, Xi'an 710061, China

Frederick Nii Ofei Bruce

School of Astronautics, Northwestern Polytechnical University, Xi'an 710072, China

Daniel Ewusi Arthur

Department of Economics, Applied Statistics and International Business, New Mexico State University, Las Cruces, New Mexico, United States

Michael Provide Fumey

School of Public Policy and Administration, Northwestern Polytechnical University, Xian 710072, Shaanxi, China

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Abstract

Autonomous vehicles (AVs) have inspired tremendous interest in solving existing transportation sector difficulties, especially with recent breakthroughs in sustainable ways of transportation. However, theoretical frameworks or models to efficiently analyze the threats, challenges, opportunities, and sustainability associated with AVs' usage remain limited in application. This study introduces the Problem Cause Solution Sustainability Advantage Disadvantage Threat Opportunities (PC-SSADTO) conceptual framework, a modified form of the Strength Weaknesses Opportunities Threats (SWOT) analysis to analyze AVs as a sustainable solution. This framework examines the difficulties, risks, and possibilities of using AVs in the transportation sector as well as how their worldwide implementation and integration might help lower carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions, enhance road safety, and improve mobility and accessibility, thus accelerating the accomplishment of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The requirements of the PC-SSADTO framework are confirmed by a survey that gathers over 200 public answers on the present issues or challenges that AVs may address, such as lowering traffic congestion, greenhouse gas emissions, and climate change for an improved livelihood. Despite some uncertainty in human opinions about AVs systems, the application of totally autonomous operations appears to be essential for the effective integration of AVs. Therefore, high degrees of integration with public transportation and cooperative decision-making structures would favor practical AVs implementations and usage positively.

Keywords: Autonomous vehicles, PC-SSADTO conceptual framework, public opinions, sustainable development goals (SDGs), sustainable mobility, transportation industry.

¹ Corresponding author's Email: fumeymichael3@gmail.com

Introduction

The transportation industry constantly evolves with new technologies (Blankesteyn et al., 2019; Pucihar et al., 2019; Stock, 2009) such as cars, drones (Javaid et al., 2022), hyperloops, and self-driving vehicles (Amano & Uchimura, 2018; Meng et al., 2019; Smith et al., 2022)(Façanha et al., 2012a)(Yamamoto & Talvitie, 2011). The growing concern over the environmental impact of traditional transportation (Compostella et al., 2020; Hofmann & Osterwalder, 2017; Ritchie et al., 2019) methods has led researchers to explore alternative transportation solutions. Innovations in sustainable transportation modes, such as electric, hydrogen, and biofuel vehicles, and data-driven technologies, such as intelligent traffic management, connected (Elliott et al., 2019; Yang et al., 2018) and autonomous vehicles (Ackaah et al., 2022a; Council on Clean Transportation, 2020; Faisal et al., 2019a; Rabiei et al., 2018) and shared mobility services, offer significant opportunities for sustainability and innovation in the industry (Mądział, 2024; Tu & Xu, 2024; E. Y. C. Wong et al., 2021).

However, the transportation industry has also contributed to many global problems or issues, such as traffic congestion caused by the increasing number of cars on the road, inadequate infrastructure, and pollution from vehicle emissions, which contribute to global warming. It poses health risks (Façanha et al., 2012b). Additionally, the high energy consumption of transportation and accidents remain a significant challenge. Electric vehicles (EVs) are a cleaner, more sustainable alternative to traditional gasoline-powered vehicles (Bhatti et al., 2021; Khan et al., 2021; Toglaw et al., 2018), and their development is a significant breakthrough in the transportation industry. EVs have minimal emissions and are energy-efficient (Khan et al., 2021; Khoucha et al., 2015) as they have fewer moving parts than conventional vehicles, require less maintenance, are less expensive (Bhatti et al., 2021; Khoucha et al., 2015; Toglaw et al., 2018) quieter and more efficient. They can be charged using electricity from diverse renewable sources. EVs can enhance energy security and reduce dependence on fossil fuels (Divakarla et al., 2019). They can recharge at night when electricity demand is typically lower, reducing the electricity grid demand and lowering consumer energy prices (Phan et al., 2021).

Despite EVs gaining popularity, there are challenges to their widespread adoption. These challenges include a limited driving range, higher initial or upfront cost, inadequate charging infrastructure, supply chain issues for critical materials, the environmental impact of production, the weight of the batteries affecting energy efficiency, safety concerns, and the need to standardize charging infrastructure and regulations. These challenges can be managed through battery technology, lowering the price of EVs and their components, developing charging infrastructure, creating more sustainable production processes, and operating EVs' integration with the electrical grid. While progress has been made, the transportation industry's safety requires continued attention and effort from all stakeholders involved to mitigate the challenges of EV technology further (Cui et al., 2019; Trubia et al., 2020; Wolfe, 2017; Yamamoto & Talvitie, 2011).

Another emerging technology, autonomous vehicles (AVs) (Beecham, 2018; Zipper, 2020), could address some challenges associated with EVs and the transportation industry (Hafeez et al., 2020; Huajun et al., 2020; Shabanpour et al., 2018; Yuen et al., 2021)., and

contribute to several Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). (Guenat et al., 2022). The development of AVs (Faisal et al., 2019b; Tsekeris & Tsekeris, 2011a; Yurtsever et al., 2020) (Hansen et al., n.d.; Silva et al., 2022; Tsekeris & Tsekeris, 2011b) such as self-driving cars (Economist, 2015), trucks, and drones, and intelligent infrastructure using sensors and cameras to monitor traffic, data analytics to optimize transportation systems (Millard-Ball, 2018), and the emergence of new market entrants like ride-sharing and on-demand delivery companies that disrupt traditional models, is transforming the transportation of goods (Mariani et al., 2021) with autonomous delivery. (Andraško et al., 2021; Baker & Wagner, 2013; Talebian & Mishra, 2018); AVs can reduce traffic congestion and accidents and improve access to transportation and logistics. (Chattopadhyay et al., 2021; Zhang & Guhathakurta, 2021).

Advances have pushed the expansion of autonomous vehicles in machine learning, artificial intelligence, and sensor technology (Kong & Fu, 2022; Kwon & Ju, 2021). These technologies enable AVs or self-driving (Ackaah et al., 2022b) to perceive the environment, make decisions (Pendleton et al., 2017), and control their movement on the road. AVs can decrease traffic congestion flow (Kerner, 2021) and trip time by using sensors, detectors, and communication technologies to communicate with each other and the surrounding infrastructure and reduce bottlenecks caused by human-driven vehicles. As a result, travel time is reduced, and the transportation system's efficiency is improved. Autonomous vehicles improve safety and decrease emissions by optimizing their routes, speed, energy or fuel consumption, and driving behaviors. Also, they help promote shared vehicle usefulness, lowering the number of cars on the road and curbing emissions. This contributes to a greener and more sustainable future. Autonomous vehicles can make transportation more accessible for people who cannot operate a vehicle, increasing their independence and quality of life. Integrating AV technology with electric and hybrid-electric vehicles can further reduce environmental pollution (Compostella et al., 2020). Figure 1 summarizes the trend of the transportation industry toward AVs.

Figure 1. Source: Own figure based on the Journey toward Autonomous Vehicles.

Despite the many advantages of AVs' usage, AVs also pose some disadvantages and threats. Moreover, the transition to AVs may prove difficult and expensive, with many stakeholders needing to upgrade their infrastructure. The importance of sustainable mobility and development has been reinforced by the growing recognition of the problems caused by climate change (Façanha et al., 2012c). The introduction of AVs into transportation systems is not only a technological and economic issue but also raises significant ethical concerns that must be addressed by policymakers, industry stakeholders, and researchers. There have been increasing concerns about autonomous vehicles' safety and whether they will increase vehicle travel and congestion. Communication systems are used to improve traffic flow and avoid accidents. Safety systems like collision avoidance and emergency braking are also critical. AVs' user-friendly, human-machine interface and cybersecurity are crucial for safety (Haboucha et al., 2017). Further research should examine AVs' long-term impacts and determine any drawbacks or obstacles to widespread adoption involved (Cui et al., 2019; Trubia et al., 2020; Wolfe, 2017; Yamamoto & Talvitie, 2011).

One of the most pressing ethical concerns surrounding AVs is privacy. AVs rely on vast amounts of data collected through sensors, cameras, and communication systems to navigate roads and interact with other vehicles and infrastructure. This data often includes sensitive information such as location tracking, driving habits, and even the identification of passengers and pedestrians. Without robust data protection mechanisms, AV systems may inadvertently expose individuals to privacy risks, such as unauthorized data collection, surveillance, or hacking. As AVs become more integrated with networked infrastructure and other vehicles, they become vulnerable to cyberattacks. Such attacks could compromise vehicle safety, lead to collisions, or expose sensitive user data. To mitigate these risks, policymakers must enforce stringent data protection laws and cybersecurity standards (Nazerdeylami et al., 2021). Another significant ethical issue is the potential displacement of jobs due to the widespread adoption of AVs, particularly in the transportation and logistics industries. Truck drivers, taxi drivers, delivery personnel, and public transit operators could face unemployment as AVs take over their roles. While AV technology promises increased efficiency and safety, it may also lead to significant societal disruptions, especially for lower-income individuals who rely on driving as a primary source of income. To address these concerns, governments must consider implementing workforce retraining programs and social safety nets to assist those whose jobs may be affected by automation. Policymakers should focus on creating new opportunities in industries that support AV deployment, such as AV maintenance, cybersecurity, and data analysis.

AVs rely heavily on machine learning algorithms to make decisions, such as detecting obstacles, predicting pedestrian behavior, and choosing the safest driving routes. However, like any machine learning system, AV algorithms are prone to bias. Bias can arise from the data used to train the system or the algorithms' design. For instance, if AVs are trained primarily in urban environments, they may perform poorly in rural areas. Similarly, suppose pedestrian detection systems are trained using predominantly one demographic group; they may not accurately detect individuals from other groups. Algorithmic bias in AVs could have serious consequences, including increased accident rates for specific populations or environments. To counteract this, developers of AV technologies must prioritize fairness and inclusivity in their algorithmic design, ensuring

that the data used to train AV systems is diverse and representative of the real-world environments in which they will operate. There is a need for continuous monitoring of AV systems to ensure fairness and reduce the risk of biased decision-making. AVs' technology's dual-use nature necessitates carefully considering how these systems are designed, deployed, and controlled. These issues bring a growing need for a comprehensive framework to analyze the impact of AVs on sustainability and transportation systems. While AV technology holds promise for contributing to sustainable development goals (SDGs), there is a lack of robust theoretical models or frameworks that can adequately assess the challenges, opportunities, and broader implications of AV adoption. The critical problems include the absence of a unified framework that incorporates sustainability, social equity, environmental impacts, and technological challenges related to AVs.

In this work, we developed the PC-SSADTO conceptual framework that stems from some existing conceptual models such as the Strength-Weaknesses-Opportunities-Threats (SWOT) analysis by integrating sustainability and ethical dimensions to analyze the effectiveness of AVs as an innovation in the transportation sector, analyze the potential of AVs to reduce traffic congestion, assess their role in mitigating environmental impact, and evaluate their contribution to road safety. With confirmation of this concept by a realistic public view collected in a survey of the current challenges that AVs could solve, this study holds significant importance as it addresses a critical gap in the literature by developing a comprehensive theoretical framework specifically tailored to assess AVs' sustainability and ethical and technological challenges. By conducting a survey, the study offers empirical insights into public perceptions of AVs, particularly regarding their perceived benefits, challenges, and risks. These insights contribute to understanding how AV technology is viewed by different demographic groups and in various regions, shedding light on factors influencing AV acceptance. The study bridges multiple disciplines, including transportation planning, environmental science, and ethics, contributing a multi-dimensional perspective on adopting AV technology. This interdisciplinary approach broadens the understanding of how AVs can be integrated into society sustainably. The PC-SSADTO framework provides a practical tool for policymakers to assess the potential impacts of AV technology on sustainability goals and social equity. Using this framework, policymakers can better develop regulations and policies that ensure AVs contribute positively to societal welfare while addressing critical issues like privacy, cybersecurity, and job displacement. The findings offer valuable insights for AV manufacturers, transport companies, and urban planners.

Related Works

The development and adoption of AVs have significant benefits for society. Still, it is also essential to consider and address any adverse impacts and potential downsides to adopting autonomous vehicles.(Severino et al., 2021). Transformed industries may experience job losses, regional differences in infrastructure and regulations (Schuelke-Leech et al., 2019) that may negatively impact the cost-benefit analysis or the economy (De Jong, 2019), privacy and cybersecurity concerns with a fully autonomous system (Dave et al., 2019). The need for robust conceptual frameworks and models to analyze and evaluate the impacts and benefits of autonomous vehicles is a critical challenge in adopting and deploying AVs. Some existing frameworks and models focus on the

technical aspects of autonomous vehicles. In contrast, others focus on the social and economic impacts (Nikitas et al., 2021). Table 1 summarizes the existing models and frameworks that analyze AVs.

Table 1. Existing Models and Frameworks Related to Autonomous Vehicles

Criteria	Existing Models and Frameworks	Focus, Findings, and Key Contributions of The Paper
Problem	Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) Theory of planned behavior (TPB) Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT), (Rejali et al., 2023)	The study on user acceptance of Fully Automated Vehicles (FAVs) revealed that most participants expressed a high willingness to use FAVs in the future, despite 49.4% having no prior knowledge of them. The research demonstrated that the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), and Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) effectively explained users' behavioral intentions. Among these, the TPB model was identified as the most accurate predictor of acceptance, followed by UTAUT and TAM. The findings emphasize the significance of subjective norms and attitudes toward FAVs in influencing acceptance, offering insights for marketing and communication strategies. This study provides a foundation for future research on FAVs' acceptance and usage behavior.
	24-model (Yan et al., 2021)	Investigated eleven significant accidents involving commercial vehicles in China, analyzing their characteristics in terms of time, location, vehicle types, and causation using the 24-model framework. The findings revealed that most accidents occurred during the daytime, with a peak during rush hours. Highways and expressways, particularly in urban areas, were the most common locations for these accidents. Heavy-duty trucks were the most frequently involved vehicles, followed by buses and light-duty trucks. The study identified several key factors contributing to these accidents, including driver fatigue, overloading, speeding, poor vehicle maintenance, and adverse weather and road conditions.
	Traffic-flow theory (Tsuboi, 2021)	Conducted a real traffic congestion analysis in a major Indian city, using innovative traffic flow analysis methods and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) to identify congested areas. It found that the most congested location was near a major intersection, with significant differences in traffic flow between peak and off-peak times. The authors proposed several solutions to mitigate congestion, such as enhancing public transportation systems, implementing intelligent transportation systems (ITS), and promoting alternative modes of transportation like cycling and walking.
	2SFCA model (Yoon & Park, 2022)	Analyzed primary care accessibility for older adults using public transportation. It highlighted the crucial role of integrating medical and transportation links in urban planning strategies. It emphasized that urban planning should consider the distribution of socially disadvantaged populations and public service facilities to ensure equitable access. The key contributions of the study include providing urban planning implications that advocate for more integrated planning to create a fairer and more accessible city for all residents.

Criteria	Existing Models and Frameworks	Focus, Findings, and Key Contributions of The Paper
	Multi-level perspective (MLP) (Wu et al., 2021)	Analyzed the three MLP layers—landscape, regime, and niche—across different phases of China’s new energy vehicles (NEV) development, including pre-development, take-off, acceleration, and sprint. It identified key factors influencing the transition at each level of the socio-technical system, such as policy support, technological innovation, and consumer demand, which were crucial in shaping the NEV landscape in China. The study offers valuable insights into technological transitions within complex socio-technical systems. It underscores the importance of adopting a holistic perspective when analyzing these processes.
	Innovation diffusion theory (IDT) (Yuen et al., 2020)	Identified the factors influencing public acceptance of autonomous vehicles. It found that the impact of innovation diffusion attributes on public acceptance is fully mediated by the public’s perceived value of these vehicles. Additionally, the effect of perceived value on acceptance is partially mediated by the public’s trust in autonomous vehicles. The study offers valuable insights into technology-human interactions. It suggests implications for transport policies and practices to manage better and understand public acceptance of autonomous vehicles.
	Urban Mobility Index (UMI) (Moeinaddini et al., 2015)	Focused on evaluating transportation in cities at the macro level. It found that factors such as population and employment density, employment ratio, mixed land use, non-motorized environment design variables like walking facilities and route directness, and accessibility to other activities significantly influence vehicle usage ratios. The study highlights that the Urban Mobility Index (UMI) can be utilized to identify existing transportation issues and propose solutions for reducing car usage.
	Average kilometers traveled (AKT) (Sayyadi & Awasthi, 2020)	Focused on ranking evaluation criteria and alternatives for sustainable transportation policies. It introduced an integrated approach combining system dynamics (SD) simulation and analytic network process (ANP) to evaluate five policies—trip sharing (TRS), trip rate reduction (TRR), reducing the length of the road network (LRN), car ownership (CAO), and average kilometers traveled (AKT)—against three criteria: congestion level (CONG), fuel consumption (FULC), and emissions (EMIS). The study found that trip-sharing-based policies perform better than the others in achieving sustainability in the transportation system.
	The socio-technical approach (Marletto, 2019)	Focused on accounting for competition between different networks of innovators in shaping the impact of automated driving on urban mobility. The paper examined technological, business, and policy innovations using a socio-technical approach while emphasizing urban quality and sustainable transportation in the transition toward automated driving. It identified three distinct transition pathways towards automated driving, each led by a different network of innovators, and utilized socio-technical maps to illustrate the outcomes of each pathway.

Criteria	Existing Models and Frameworks	Focus, Findings, and Key Contributions of The Paper
	Multi-agent transport model (Vosooghi et al., 2020)	Investigated the infrastructure changes required to introduce autonomous electric vehicles, focusing on the performance of electric vehicle (EV) battery charging stations. The findings concluded that the optimal charging solution combines fast and regular chargers to enhance charging speed. Additionally, the study highlighted the need to reduce the distance between charging stations to alleviate the load on individual stations and improve service quality for users.
Cause	Emissions Inventory Model (M. Li et al., 2017; Peng et al., 2022)	Reviewed the progress in developing inventories of anthropogenic emissions, emphasizing the need for comprehensive research and control of air pollution emissions from ships to promote low-carbon, green, and sustainable development. The key contribution of the research is the improvement of the calculation model for the power method emission inventory tailored to the specifics of ships operating in inland river areas. This advancement provides valuable insights for developing and refining emission inventories in these regions.
Sustainability	Sustainability and technology assessment concept (Nemoto et al., 2021)	Focused on defining a method to measure the impact of shared automated electric vehicles. It reviewed existing research on how autonomous vehicles affect urban mobility. The key contributions include the identification of 20 indicators to analyze this impact, encompassing aspects such as safety, accessibility, noise pollution, and economic profitability.
	Life cycle assessment (LCA) method (H. Li et al., 2019)	Assessed the environmental impact of emissions throughout the life cycle of a transportation infrastructure project. It found that the construction phase had the highest environmental impact, accounting for 62.7% of the total, followed by the demolition phase at 35.8% and the maintenance phase at 1.7%. Among the materials used, steel was identified as having the largest share of environmental impact during the construction phase, contributing 55.5%. The key contribution of the study is its identification of the most significant phase and material sources of environmental impact, providing insights for reducing emissions throughout the project lifecycle.
	The structural analysis-MICMAC method (Chatziioannou et al., 2023)	Used a structural analysis- Impact Matrix Cross-Reference Multiplication Applied to a Classification (MICMAC) method to rank sustainable urban mobility indicators and corresponding transport policies. It identified several critical indicators essential for promoting livable city futures. It matched them with supportive transport policies, including improvements in public transportation, development of cycling infrastructure, pedestrianization of city center streets, and the creating of low-emission vehicle zones in urban areas. The study's essential contribution demonstrates the importance of aligning sustainable urban mobility indicators with effective transport policies.
	SWOT analysis (Perra et al., 2017)	Focused on identifying the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats (SWOT) related to sustainable urban mobility. It emphasized the importance of sustainable urban mobility in achieving sustainable development goals. The paper's essential contribution is demonstrating that urban mobility plays a crucial role in shaping the quality of life in cities and has significant implications for economic, social, and environmental sustainability.

Criteria	Existing Models and Frameworks	Focus, Findings, and Key Contributions of The Paper
	Global Protocol for Community-Scale Greenhouse Gas Emission Inventories (GPC) (Ahn et al., 2023; Yuen et al., 2020)	Provided an overview of the C40 Cities Climate Leadership Group and its objective of achieving net-zero emissions by 2050. It highlights the critical need for precise greenhouse gas emission calculations at the city level to meet this goal. It compares emission calculations using different datasets to identify areas for improvement in emission inventories. The critical contribution of the study is its finding that the quality of emission factors (EFs) used in greenhouse gas inventories varies regionally, with European and North American cities having the highest quality data. In contrast, African and Latin American cities have the lowest.
	SILENT Model	The paper introduces the Sustainable Infrastructure, Land-use, Environment and Transport Model (SILENT) as an advanced geographic information system and indicator-based comparative urban sustainability indexing model. It outlines the model's conceptual framework and components, including developing an indicator base, urban sustainability indexing base, and policy and decision support base. The critical contribution of the study is demonstrating that the SILENT model can assist planners and policymakers in implementing an integrated framework for sustainability policies that can be adapted to local contexts.
	Sustainable Urban Mobility Transitions (SUMT) (Loo, 2021)	Focused on advancing a paradigm shift in transportation by presenting a people-oriented and place-based framework for measuring and promoting walkable cities. It emphasizes the importance of quantifying walking-related variables in transport design manuals and ensuring a seamless transportation experience for individuals using sustainable transport modes. The paper's key contributions are its strategic directions for integrating these variables into transport design and enhancing the overall experience of sustainable transport.
	Traffic simulation-based approach (García de Soto et al., 2018)	Investigated the carbon footprint of autonomous electric vehicles (AEVs) in urban areas, comparing their impact under different conditions of use, including urban driving and highway driving. The key findings reveal that AEVs notably impact greenhouse gas emissions throughout their lifecycle, including production, maintenance, and recycling. The study's primary contribution is highlighting the significant environmental impact of AEVs beyond their operation, stressing the need to consider these factors in assessing their overall sustainability.

While these frameworks and models help address specific aspects of the AVs' challenges, a lack of a unified conceptual framework or theoretical model makes it difficult for policymakers, industry leaders, and other stakeholders to evaluate autonomous vehicles' benefits and drawbacks fully. There is also a growing need for a conceptual framework to analyze their impact on the industry (Haarmann et al., 2012; Lin, 2016; Wong et al., 2017), identifying critical research directions (Barghuthi et al., 2018) (Jain et al., 2021) focusing on the equity (Guo et al., 2020a) implications of AVs (Guo et al., 2020b; Hail & McQuaid, 2021) such as affordability, the digital divide, and societal norms (Yao et al., 2021). There has yet to be a consensus on a single conceptual

framework for analyzing AVs in the transportation industry (Stephenson, 2013). There is a need for various frameworks (Deo et al., 2018) that offer valuable insights into the impacts of AVs in different dimensions (Pouya & Madni, 2021; Sung et al., 2020). Therefore, further research and development are necessary to optimize the technology, address security concerns and ethical considerations, establish appropriate regulatory frameworks, and ensure public acceptance (Janatabadi & Ermagun, 2022; Othman, 2021) of autonomous vehicles as safe and reliable modes of transportation (Ribeiro et al., 2022).

To provide a more comprehensive understanding of the challenges and opportunities associated with Autonomous Vehicles (AVs), it is crucial to incorporate perspectives from policymakers, transportation planners, and ethicists. Policymakers are central in shaping the regulatory landscape, influencing AV technology's success and public acceptance. They must address complex issues such as data privacy, cybersecurity, and the legal liability framework for AV-related accidents. Transportation planners must reimagine urban infrastructure to accommodate AVs, investing in smart roads, dedicated AV lanes, and connected communication systems. Their focus must include integrating AVs with public transportation systems to reduce congestion and emissions, promoting a shift toward shared mobility, and reducing individual car ownership. From an ethical perspective, AVs introduce significant concerns around decision-making algorithms, particularly in critical, life-threatening scenarios. Ethicists emphasize the need for fairness and inclusivity in AV algorithms, which must be designed to avoid biases that could disproportionately affect vulnerable groups, such as minorities or people in rural areas. AV systems raise moral questions about privacy, as the extensive data they gather could be used for surveillance or targeted advertising. Ensuring robust protections against misuse of this data is critical to maintaining public trust. Policymakers and ethicists must work together to address these issues, ensuring that the adoption of AVs aligns with social equity, protects individual rights, and fosters public confidence in the technology.

Conceptual Framework

Problem-Cause-Solution-Sustainability-Advantage-Disadvantage-Threat-Opportunities (PC-SSADTO) Conceptual Framework Analysis of AVs

The introduction and related works highlighted the current state of the transportation sector and how autonomous vehicles can be a way of sustainable transportation, explaining the need for further development in the land-based transportation sector due to several challenges, the importance of the sustainability perspective, and the potential of autonomous vehicles to solve these challenges. Based on the challenges and shortcomings discussed in the literature, this study aims to investigate the essential factors for deploying AVs as a sustainable transportation option. For this, the SWOT Analysis was extended; hence, the PC-SSADTO conceptual framework was proposed. With the application of this framework, a quantitative study was conducted. This leads to the following research questions in exploring this study:

1. What are the implications of integrating autonomous vehicles with existing public transportation systems for enhancing overall urban mobility and reducing congestion?

2. How can autonomous vehicles contribute to reducing carbon emissions in various types of urban and rural settings?
3. What are the potential economic impacts of widespread AV adoption on different sectors, including automotive manufacturing, insurance, and urban planning?
4. How might the widespread adoption of autonomous vehicles influence social equity and accessibility to transportation in underserved communities?
5. What are the potential changes in driving behavior and road safety with the introduction of autonomous vehicles, and how can these be measured and managed?
6. How can public perceptions and acceptance of autonomous vehicles be improved to facilitate their adoption and integration into existing transportation systems?
7. What are the critical regulatory and policy challenges associated with deploying autonomous vehicles, and how can these be addressed to ensure safety and innovation?
8. How can governments incentivize the adoption of autonomous vehicles in a way that aligns with sustainability goals and supports infrastructure development?
9. What are the legal and ethical implications of decision-making algorithms in autonomous vehicles, particularly in scenarios involving unavoidable harm?

To supplement the existing models and frameworks related to autonomous vehicles, as highlighted in Table 1, especially with the underlying theory of the SWOT model, the PC-SSADTO conceptual framework's components illustrated in Fig. 2 are valuable for analyzing autonomous vehicles. Each component can identify and explore different aspects of the technology, providing a comprehensive understanding of its practical benefits and challenges. By studying how these factors contribute to the overall development and implementation of autonomous vehicles, stakeholders will better understand the implications of this emerging technology.

With the detailed PC-SSADTO framework, as shown in Table 2, highlighting some of the global problems that autonomous vehicles are helping to solve, along with their causes, solutions, advantages, disadvantages, threats, and opportunities, it will be easier to identify the benefits and challenges associated with autonomous vehicles and to develop strategies for their successful integration into society.

Figure 2. PC-SSADTO Conceptual Framework

Table 2. Detailed PC-SSADTO Conceptual Framework

Problem	Cause	Solution	Sustainability (SDG goals approach)	Advantage	Disadvantage	Threats	Opportunities
Industry <i>Delivery of goods and transportation of humans</i>	Inefficient supply chains and delivery routes	Increase the efficiency of the delivery of goods and transportation of people.	Industry, innovation, and infrastructure (SDG 9) Sustainable Cities and Communities (SDG 11) Responsible Consumption and Production (SDG 12) Partnerships for the goals (SDG 17)	Increased efficiency and productivity	High cost of technology, maintenance, and infrastructure.	Regulatory and liability issues Job displacement	Increased demand for automated logistics services
People <i>Inaccessibility</i>	Limited access to transportation in low-income and marginalized communities. Limited transportations options	Autonomous vehicles can provide affordable and accessible transportation options.	Quality Education (SDG 4) Good Health and Well-being (SDG 3) Gender Equality (SDG 5) No Poverty (SDG 1) Zero Hunger (SDG 2)	Increased mobility and economic opportunities	High cost of technology and limited availability in some areas	Privacy and cybersecurity concerns	Reduced transportation inequality and improved social mobility
People <i>Social Inequity</i>	Disability and older adults.		Reduced Inequalities (SDG 10)	Increased mobility and independence for people with disabilities			Improved quality of life for people with disabilities
People <i>Road accidents</i>	Human error, distracted driving, and fatigue. Drug and alcohol influence Poor infrastructure Complex driving scenarios or terrains	Autonomous vehicles use sensors, cameras, and machine-learning algorithms to detect and avoid collisions.	Peace, justice, and strong institutions (SDG 16) Good Health and Well-being (SDG 3) Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure (SDG 9) Sustainable Cities and Communities (SDG 11)	Reduced risk of accidents and fatalities	High cost of technology and maintenance, public skepticism about safety.	Cybersecurity threats that could cause accidents	New job opportunities in the AV industry
People	Traffic congestion and long commutes	Autonomous vehicles can allow passengers to work or relax during their commute.	Decent Work and Economic Growth (SDG 8)	Increased productivity and reduced stress	High cost of technology and	Increased demand for ride-sharing and carpooling	Improved work-life balance and

Problem	Cause	Solution	Sustainability (SDG goals approach)	Advantage	Disadvantage	Threats	Opportunities
<i>Unproductivity and Efficiency</i>			Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure (SDG 9)		maintenance, probable job displacement		economic opportunities Increased adoption of renewable energy
<i>Environment Pollution</i>	Carbon emissions from the cars cause air pollution. Oil, fuel, and chemicals from the cars contaminate water sources. Engines create noise pollution.	Autonomous vehicles (AVs) can help mitigate air and noise pollution by using quieter electric powertrains or clean energy and reducing congestion and idling.	Sustainable cities and communities (SDG 11) Clean Water and Sanitation (SDG 6) Climate action (SDG 13) Life Below Water (SDG 14) Life on land (SDG 15) Affordable and Clean Energy (SDG 7)	Reduced environmental impact	High cost of AVs and infrastructures	Increased demand for electricity and battery production	Increased adoption of renewable energy
<i>Environment Depletion of Natural Resources</i>	Use of natural resources for manufacturing of Vehicles	Autonomous vehicles (AVs) can reduce the depletion of natural resources by using renewable energy, such as solar or wind power, to charge their batteries.	Affordable and Clean Energy (SDG 7) Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure (SDG 9) Sustainable Cities and Communities (SDG 11) Responsible Consumption and Production (SDG 12)	AVs reduce natural resource depletion through renewable energy, optimized routes, and extended battery life, reducing production and replacement needs.	Resource-intensive production of batteries	Environmental impacts from renewable energy infrastructure and the resource-intensive production of batteries can lead to increased mining and waste generation.	Reducing natural resource depletion, promoting sustainable infrastructure and renewable energy

Methodology

Survey Design and Administration

The methodology of this study begins with the “*survey design phase*,” where the survey objectives are defined and the questionnaire is crafted. The survey aims to collect data on how AVs can address environmental challenges and contribute to sustainability. The questions capture demographic information, participants’ perceptions of environmental issues, and their opinions on AVs. The survey includes multiple-choice questions, rating scales, and open-ended questions to ensure comprehensive data collection. This stage is followed by the “*Create Survey Form stage*,” where the survey is constructed using Microsoft Office Forms. This step involves setting up the survey with the designed questions and ensuring the form is ready for distribution. The form is created to be user-friendly and accurately reflect the survey’s objectives. Before the full launch, a “*Pre-Test Survey*” is conducted to test the clarity and effectiveness of the questions. This pilot test, done on ten people, helps identify any issues with the questions or the survey format, ensuring that the final version is easy to understand and effectively gathers the desired information.

The survey is then distributed through social media platforms such as WeChat, WhatsApp, X (formerly Twitter), LinkedIn, and Facebook. Participants are invited to take the survey, and a brief description of the survey’s purpose and instructions is provided to facilitate participation. The survey targeted respondents via social media, resulting in a predominantly younger, educated sample size. Participants complete the survey at their convenience within eight weeks. During the “*Monitor Participation phase*,” the survey’s progress is tracked. This step ensures sufficient responses and helps identify and address any issues that may arise during the data collection period. After the survey period ends, the “*Data Collection phase*” begins, and the collected responses are downloaded from the online survey platform for further processing.

The collected data is reviewed for accuracy and completeness in the “*Ensure Data Quality stage*.” This process involves checking for response inconsistencies or errors to ensure reliable data. The next step is “*Data Preparation*,” where the extracted data from the survey platform is formatted for analysis. This stage includes cleaning and organizing the data to prepare it for statistical evaluation. The “*Prepare Data for Analysis*” stage involves further organizing and processing the data to make it suitable for detailed analysis. This step ensures the data is in the correct format and ready for statistical tools. Once the data is prepared, it is “*Imported into Analysis Software*.” Our study uses Origin (2022 Version) statistical software to analyze the data. The “*Analyze Data phase*” involves performing statistical analyses to summarize the data, identify trends and patterns, and determine relationships between variables using inferential statistics.

After analyzing the data, the next step is to “*Interpret Results*.” This involves understanding the implications of the statistical findings and how they relate to the survey’s objectives. Reporting and interpretation involve documenting the results and their significance. This stage includes preparing reports summarizing the findings and their implications for the study on AVs and environmental sustainability. The *Prepare*

Report phase involves creating a detailed report based on the findings. This report includes a comprehensive data analysis and interpretations that address the survey’s objectives. In the *Discuss Limitations stage*, the limitations of the survey method are addressed. This includes acknowledging potential biases, the reliance on self-reported data, and the applicability of the findings to different contexts. In our study, while this demographic is critical for understanding perceptions of emerging technologies like AVs, it may limit the generalizability of older or less-educated populations. Future studies could aim to include a more diverse sample. Based on the study’s findings and limitations, recommendations for future research have been developed. This includes suggesting areas for further investigation, such as introducing additional theoretical lenses to analyze AVs as an innovation. Finally, the results are disseminated to relevant stakeholders and the wider public. This step ensures that the findings are shared and can contribute to ongoing discussions and research. The last phase is to collect feedback on the survey process and findings. Feedback is gathered from participants and stakeholders to refine future surveys and research approaches. Fig. 3 highlights each stage of the survey workflow, from design to data analysis and reporting, and addresses the limitations and recommendations for future research.

Figure 3. Survey Process on Autonomous Vehicles and Environmental Sustainability.

Results and Discussion

Results from the Survey

The survey asked participants for their demographic information, including gender, age, educational background, occupation status, and geographical location. Out of 209 responses, Table 3 summarizes the data collected on the demographics and basic information.

Table 3. Summary of Demographics

Category	Description	Percentage (%)
Educational Background	High school	5.26
	Bachelor	32.54
	Masters	43.54
	Ph.D. and Above	16.27
	Others	2.39
Occupation	Student	33.49
	Parent	2.87
	Employer	0.48
	Employee	35.41
	Unemployed	3.35
	Others	24.40
Current Location	Africa	26.79
	Europe	2.87
	Asia	37.80
	North-America	30.62
	South-America	0.48
	Antarctica	0
	Australia	0.48
Others	0.96	
Age	18-24	23.44
	25-34	58.37
	35-44	15.31
	45-54	1.91
	Above 54	0.96
Gender	Male	70.87
	Female	29.13

The survey results comprehensively collate the public's perception of AVs and their potential to address key challenges in the transportation sector. Demographic data from Table 3 indicates that most respondents were aged between 25-34 (58.37%), with a significant number holding either a Bachelor's or Master's degree. This demographic is particularly important, as their awareness and understanding of AV technology could influence the overall results. At the beginning of the survey, the participants were asked whether they already had the opportunity to test or had used the AVs in the past. Most respondents were students (33.49%) or employees (35.41%), suggesting that the survey captured the views of future and current workforce members, many of whom may be directly impacted by AVs. While our sample skews towards a younger and more educated demographic, this reflects the most likely to engage with autonomous vehicle technologies. However, this overrepresentation may limit the generalizability of the results to the broader population, particularly older and less educated groups. Future studies should aim for more diverse sampling to reduce this bias.

Respondents came from various regions, with a significant proportion from Asia (37.80%) and North America (30.62%). This geographical diversity offers insights into how perceptions of AVs might vary across regions with different infrastructure and levels of technological development. In developed regions with advanced transportation networks, such as North America and parts of Europe, the integration of AVs may be smoother due to well-established road systems, higher investment in smart infrastructure, and greater technological readiness. These regions have the financial capacity to support the substantial infrastructure upgrades needed for AV implementation, including smart traffic management systems, communication networks, and charging stations for electric AVs. Additionally, the demographic in these areas, characterized by higher levels of technological literacy and public acceptance of innovation, may facilitate a faster adoption rate. Economically developed regions are also more likely to have regulatory frameworks to address liability, data privacy, and cybersecurity issues, which are crucial for the successful deployment of AVs.

In contrast, the impact of AVs in developing regions may be more constrained by underdeveloped infrastructure and limited financial resources. In many parts of Africa, Asia, and Latin America, roads are often poorly maintained, and existing transportation systems may not be equipped to support the sophisticated requirements of AV technology. These regions may also face challenges related to a lack of investment in smart infrastructure and reliable internet or cellular networks essential for the operation of connected AV systems. Moreover, the demographic characteristics of these regions, including lower levels of technological literacy and economic disparity, may lead to slower public adoption of AVs. In rural areas and regions with less dense populations, the economic viability of AVs could be questioned, as the costs associated with upgrading infrastructure may outweigh the perceived benefits. However, AVs could still offer significant opportunities in these regions, particularly in improving transportation access for underserved or remote communities, potentially enhancing mobility and economic development if supported by targeted investments and policies.

The survey also gathered responses from 209 participants, providing insights into the public's perceptions of AVs and their potential to address transportation challenges such as traffic congestion, environmental impact, and road safety. Respondents ranked traffic congestion as one of the most significant transportation challenges, with an average score of 4.32 out of 5. These results indicate widespread concern about traffic congestion and highlight the potential for AVs to mitigate this issue by optimizing traffic flow and reducing human error. Another primary concern was environmental impact and pollution, with an average score of 4.21. This finding supports the idea that AVs, particularly electric or hybrid ones, could be crucial in reducing emissions and promoting cleaner transportation. Road safety was also a significant concern, scoring an average of 4.15. Respondents believed AVs could reduce accidents by eliminating human error, a leading cause of road accidents. Accessibility challenges, including outdated infrastructure, were rated with an average score of 4.07. This indicates that while AVs could improve mobility, significant infrastructure upgrades would be required for widespread adoption. These individual results highlight the public's recognition of AVs as a potential solution to many pressing transportation issues but also emphasize the challenges that need to be addressed, particularly in terms of infrastructure and public acceptance. The high concentration of younger, highly educated respondents may contribute to the overall

optimism toward AV adoption, as younger individuals are typically more open to technological innovations. However, this optimism may not reflect the views of older or less technologically inclined populations, indicating a potential bias in the survey results. Table 4 highlights the perceived challenges in transportation. Table 4 further gives some background on the statistics obtained from the survey.

Table 4. Statistics of the responses collected

Challenges	Average	Standard Deviation	(%) of Score 1	(%) of Score 2	(%) of Score 3	(%) of Score 4	(%) of Score 5
Traffic Congestion	4.32	0.98	1.91	4.31	15.31	19.14	59.81
Road Safety or Security	4.15	1.12	1.91	11.00	11.48	21.05	54.54
Environmental Impact and Pollution	4.21	1.02	1.43	5.26	19.14	19.14	55.02
Accessibility and Aging Infrastructure	4.07	1.16	3.83	8.61	15.31	21.53	50.72
Logistics or Transport of Goods	4.09	1.14	3.83	7.18	15.79	22.49	50.72
Parking Space	4.06	1.11	2.39	6.22	24.88	15.79	50.72
Unproductivity and Inefficiency	4.12	1.04	2.87	3.83	19.62	25.84	47.85
Lack of innovative, disruptive technologies	3.96	1.12	2.39	9.09	23.44	20.54	44.50
Social Inequity	3.83	1.15	3.83	8.61	27.27	21.53	38.76
Urbanization and Land Use	4.15	1.00	1.44	5.74	17.70	26.79	48.33

As shown in Table 4, traffic congestion remains the top concern among respondents, with an average score of 4.32. This reinforces the hypothesis that AVs can play a critical role in alleviating congestion through optimized traffic flows. The results indicate that public perceptions of AVs are generally positive, with most respondents believing that AVs can significantly reduce traffic congestion, environmental pollution, and road accidents. However, certain limitations must be addressed for successful AV integration. The environmental benefits of AVs were recognized, particularly in terms of reducing emissions when paired with electric powertrains. As Table 4 shows, respondents gave high importance to the potential of AVs to curb greenhouse gas emissions. Public sentiment strongly favored the view that AVs could reduce accidents caused by human error, aligning with the perception that automation could enhance road safety (Table 4). However, the concerns about infrastructure costs and privacy risks (as shown in the survey responses) indicate that even within these demographic groups, hesitation remains regarding full-scale AV implementation.

The PC-SSADTO framework combined with the survey is an effective model for analyzing AVs' potential contributions to sustainability. For example, respondents acknowledged that AVs could mitigate environmental impacts through reduced emissions, traffic congestion, and better energy efficiency. However, concerns about the high infrastructure costs and job displacement were frequently mentioned, pointing to the need for a balanced approach in policy-making. One significant finding is the public's hesitation towards AVs due to privacy and cybersecurity concerns. These concerns and the fear of job displacement present significant barriers to AV adoption. This suggests that while AVs may address critical environmental challenges, further work is needed to

mitigate these concerns through regulatory frameworks and technological advancements. Despite these challenges, AVs promise to enhance accessibility and social equity, particularly for underserved communities. Fig. 5 (a-j) shows that the data skews to the left, indicating higher frequencies for the scores between 3 and 5. This trend indicates that the participants in the survey generally rated the transportation challenges higher, suggesting that most respondents perceived traffic congestion, road safety, or environmental impact as significant, with fewer respondents rating these challenges as less significant.

Figure 5. Public Perception Towards AVs from the Survey

Some of the responses regarding the challenges from the open-ended questions summarized a few of the concerns from the respondents, such as aging infrastructure (untarred roads, inadequate amount of street lights, flooded highways and poor infrastructural planning, poorly connected road networks and vehicles in lousy shape, fewer bridges, no visible road markings), traffic congestion and over-crowding on streets, greenhouse gases emissions and air pollution, lack of parking space, inefficient public

transport systems and lack of other modes of transport, economic stability, geographical locations (mountainous and rural areas) and accessibility, unskilled drivers and irregular transportation policies, road safety (drivers, passengers, and pedestrians, road accidents). This further confirms that the issues proposed as challenges, irrespective of the demographics, remain challenging for the transportation industry. The suggested solutions also span the need for innovative and sustainable solutions such as AVs and policies to regulate the transport industry and its growth. The responses from the respondents on how valid AVs are an effective solution to the current challenges of the transportation industry can be summarized in Fig. 6.

Figure 6. Frequency Distribution of AVs as a solution

The results align with existing empirical literature on AV technology and its potential impacts. As Kerner (2021) noted, AVs can significantly reduce traffic congestion by optimizing traffic flow, reducing bottlenecks, and enabling more efficient use of road space. This is consistent with the survey's findings that traffic congestion remains a crucial concern, and AVs are perceived as a viable solution. The environmental benefits of AVs are well-documented, particularly when combined with electric powertrains. For example, Compostella et al. (2020) highlight the long-term potential of AVs to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and improve urban air quality. The high concern for environmental impact among respondents echoes this sentiment, suggesting that the public recognizes the environmental potential of AVs. Existing research has emphasized the potential of AVs to improve road safety by minimizing human error, a primary cause of accidents (Pendleton et al., 2017). The respondents' concerns about road safety align with this body of research, suggesting strong support for AVs to enhance safety. However, while AVs may offer improved accessibility, the survey respondents were also aware of the challenges of aging infrastructure. As Ritchie et al. (2019) indicated, outdated infrastructure presents a significant barrier to adopting AV technology, particularly in regions where roads and communication networks cannot support advanced AV systems.

The survey data indicates that a significant proportion of respondents rated AVs very positively as a solution to current transportation challenges, as illustrated in Fig. 7. With a mean score of 3.93301 and a standard deviation of 1.2692, the overall sentiment towards AVs is favorable. However, a deeper look at the data distribution reveals that many respondents rated AVs at the maximum value of 5, indicating a vivid belief in the potential of AVs to address critical issues such as traffic congestion, environmental sustainability, and road safety. The positive skew in the data, with many responses clustered at the highest score of 5, suggests that a significant portion of the population perceives AVs as a highly effective solution. This can be interpreted as an explicit public endorsement of AVs, driven by the belief that AV technology holds great promise in tackling critical transportation challenges.

Figure 7. Normal Probability Plot of AVs a solution.

Many respondents likely see AVs as a solution to traffic congestion because of their potential to optimize traffic flow, reduce human driving errors, and improve road efficiency. AVs can reduce bottlenecks and improve road network performance through advanced algorithms and real-time communication with other vehicles and infrastructure. The concentration of high scores reflects strong confidence in AVs' ability to alleviate one of the most pressing issues in urban mobility. The high "5" ratings also suggest that respondents recognize AVs' potential to contribute to environmental sustainability. Many AVs are expected to be electric or hybrid vehicles, which reduces reliance on fossil fuels and lowers greenhouse gas emissions. Furthermore, AVs can minimize unnecessary idling and optimize routes for fuel efficiency, reducing overall pollution. The positive skew supports the idea that the public views AVs as a critical component of future green transportation systems.

Another reason for the positive skew could be the widespread perception that AVs can significantly improve road safety. Autonomous systems can react faster than human drivers, avoid accidents caused by human error (such as distraction or fatigue), and follow traffic rules consistently. As road safety is a critical concern, the high ratings reflect public

optimism that AVs could reduce accidents and fatalities on the road. AVs could provide better mobility options for individuals who cannot drive, such as the elderly, disabled, or those living in underserved areas. The high positive ratings may also reflect a belief in AVs' potential to enhance transportation accessibility, ensuring that more people benefit from safer and more efficient mobility.

The positive skew in the data, with many respondents assigning the highest possible rating, indicates significant enthusiasm and optimism surrounding the introduction of AVs. This suggests that the public is mainly ready to embrace AVs as a solution to critical transportation problems, viewing them as a transformative technology with broad benefits. However, this optimism may also reflect unmet expectations or idealized views of AV technology. The public's perception of AVs as an exciting, futuristic technology that promises to solve many current problems might influence the concentration of high ratings. While AVs have substantial potential, ensuring high expectations align with realistic assessments of their deployment, challenges, and limitations is essential. The survey results, particularly the positive skew in ratings, demonstrate a strong belief in the potential of AVs to provide solutions to some of the most pressing transportation issues of our time, including traffic congestion, environmental impact, and road safety. While the data indicates overwhelming support for AVs, policymakers, industry leaders, and researchers must temper this optimism with a practical understanding of the challenges ahead, such as infrastructure development, ethical concerns, and regulatory hurdles. As the technology continues to evolve, ensuring that these high expectations are met will be vital to realizing the full potential of AVs and ensuring that they deliver on their promise of safer, cleaner, and more efficient transportation.

Conclusion

The paper presents a PC-SSADTO conceptual framework that analyses the effectiveness of AVs as an innovation in the transportation sector. With over 200 responses, the survey confirmed the PC-SSADTO framework, providing a realistic public view of the current challenges that AVs can solve. The paper argues that integrating autonomous vehicles into transportation systems can help reduce carbon emissions, increase road safety, and improve mobility and accessibility, contributing to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The findings of this study underscore the public's recognition of AVs as a potential solution to critical transportation challenges such as traffic congestion, environmental sustainability, and road safety. The survey results indicate that most respondents view AVs favorably, with a significant positive skew in the data, particularly towards the highest rating of 5. This overwhelming support suggests that the public holds high expectations for AV technology to mitigate existing transportation issues. The positive reception of AVs as a solution is driven mainly by the belief that they can *reduce traffic congestion* through advanced algorithms and autonomous control, *promote environmental sustainability* through electric or hybrid powertrains AVs, which are crucial to reducing emissions and pollution, and contribute to global sustainability goals; and *improve road safety* by minimizing accidents and eliminating human error.

However, the results also highlight specific challenges that need to be addressed for AVs to fulfill their potential. While public optimism is high, this enthusiasm must be

matched with realistic expectations about the necessary infrastructure investments, regulatory developments, and societal adaptations that will be required. Issues such as job displacement, algorithmic bias, and cybersecurity must be carefully managed to ensure that AVs do not exacerbate existing inequalities or introduce new risks. To fully realize the potential of AVs, coordinated efforts from policymakers, industry leaders, and transportation planners are necessary. Key actions include investing in smart infrastructure, addressing public concerns through education and outreach, and developing policies that ensure ethical considerations such as job displacement and data security are accounted for. Efforts should be made to educate the public on the benefits and safety of AVs, particularly in regions where acceptance is low. This can be achieved through public information campaigns and pilot programs.

Further research should focus on the ethical implications of AVs, including algorithmic bias and the potential impact on employment. Policymakers must ensure that AV adoption promotes social equity and accessibility. Continued research and development are necessary to address the technical challenges of AVs, including cybersecurity risks and ensuring safe, reliable performance under different conditions. Future research could apply the PC-SSADTO framework in diverse geographic regions to compare AV adoption's impacts in developed and developing countries. This could help understand regional differences in infrastructure, policy readiness, and public perception. Conducting longitudinal studies would provide insights into how public perceptions, infrastructure, and regulatory environments evolve as AV technology becomes more prevalent. This would also allow for the monitoring of AV impacts on employment, urban mobility, and sustainability goals.

Appendix

Survey Questions

Title: Transportation and Infrastructure Survey

Thank you for taking the time to participate in this survey on transportation and infrastructure issues. Your feedback will help us develop better policies and solutions to tackle our cities' and communities' challenges. The survey consists of multiple-choice and open-ended questions and should take about 5 minutes.

Demographic Information:

What is your age?

What is your gender?

What is your educational background?

What is your occupation?

What is your current location?

Section 1: Transportation Challenges

Please rate the following transportation challenges on a scale of 1-5, with 1 being “not significant” and 5 being “extremely significant.”

5 = Extremely significant 4 = Very significant 3 = Moderately significant 2 = Slightly significant 1 = Not significant

Traffic Congestion

Road Safety and Security

Environmental Impact and Pollution

Accessibility and Aging Infrastructure

Logistics and Transportation

Parking Space

Section 2: Infrastructure Challenges

Please rate the following infrastructure challenges on a scale of 1-5, with 1 being “not significant” and 5 being “extremely significant.”

5 = Extremely significant 4 = Very significant 3 = Moderately significant 2 = Slightly significant 1 = Not significant

Productivity and Efficiency

Social Inequity

Urbanization and Land Use

Disruptive Technologies

Open Ended-Questions

In your opinion, what does your community face as the most pressing transportation or infrastructure challenges?

What steps should be taken to address your identified transportation or infrastructure challenges?

Do you have any additional comments or suggestions about transportation or infrastructure issues in your community?

Section 3: Solutions

Are you exposed to or have some idea about autonomous or self-driving vehicles?

If yes, how would you rate autonomous vehicles as a solution to the above problems?

Conclusion: Thank you for your valuable input. Your feedback will help us identify the priorities and strategies needed to improve transportation and infrastructure in our communities.

Data and Code Availability Statement

All interpretations of the data concerning the study results have been shared in the results section. However, the complete data used in this study cannot be shared currently as they form part of an ongoing study.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the study reported in this paper.

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